

Higher Education Reform in Vietnam in the Context of a Significant Increase in the Number of Higher Education Institutions

Nguyen Mong Cam
Faculty of Law, Nam Can Tho University
Diep My Nhan
Faculty of Law, Nam Can Tho University
Nguyen Chi Hai
Faculty of Law, Nam Can Tho University

Abstract: This article focuses on analyzing the trends of higher education reform in the world, comparing them with the actual situation in the relationship between human resource training and social demand for labour, thereby proposing solutions in the educational reform process to ensure the quality of training programs. In addition, within the scope of the study, the author also mentioned the socialization of higher education leading to a significant increase in higher education institutions, potentially posing the risk of homogenization between education and businesses, ignoring the mission of training human resources. In this situation, the author proposes solutions to enhance the role of the state in inspection, examination and management of higher education towards establishing transparent and objective mechanisms in the training sector.

Keywords: education reform, university, increase, higher education institution

Introduction

Education development orientation

Reform and develop highly applicable higher education

Issues related to the socialization of university education

Conclusion

References

1. Introduction

Faced with the fluctuations of the labour market, the training orientation of educational institutions must fully meet the practical criteria of human resource needs. The slow reform of educational quality will make education unrealistic. The trained human resources do not meet the job requirements of employers, leading to a major crisis in the relationship between labour supply and demand. For example, in the current situation of education in Romania in 1995, higher education institutions faced significant difficulties in “reconnecting” their activities with the changing labour market and the needs of privatized enterprises, the international scientific and academic community.

From the above issue, it can be seen that, in the face of an economy that is always moving and developing, university education must also have fundamental innovation and be able to predict the actual changes in society regarding human resource needs in a certain period. From there, there are solutions in building training programs to develop human resources in the direction of self-study, self-research, with the ability to adapt to the practical environment, avoiding being eliminated by market rules due to outdated training knowledge. On the other hand, in the face of economic development and increasingly

modern and civilized social awareness, expectations for education are increasing, raising the issue of socializing university education to allow investment in the field of education by individuals and non-state organizations to meet social needs. However, to avoid the degeneration of education and the identification with business activities that reduce the quality of training, it is necessary to have solutions to increase the responsibility of investors in the education sector regarding their commitments to ensure training quality, as well as affirm the role of the state in inspecting and handling violations of higher education institutions.

2. Education development orientation

With 75 years of developing the education career - since the August Revolution in 1945, the Vietnamese education sector has been marking its development in a new era. During that process, the Communist Party of Vietnam has always thoroughly grasped and affirmed: education must be the top national policy, investment in education must be focused on before other fields (Associate Professor, Dr. Tran Thi Minh Tuyet, 2022).

The reform of higher education in Vietnam generally has two sacred missions, which are the responsibility of all citizens, agencies and organizations, all of whom must focus on continuous development, specifically: i) creating a fundamental and strong change in the quality and effectiveness of education and training to better meet the needs of national construction and defence and the people's learning needs; ii) Bringing Vietnamese higher education to gradually develop to international standards.

Compared with the former Soviet Union's education system or compared with the orientation of university education development in China, with the orientation of reducing the number of multidisciplinary and multidisciplinary universities and reducing enrollment quotas for majors in social sciences and humanities, instead promoting the rapid increase of educational institutions directly related to applied economics such as: polytechnics, medicine, agriculture, finance (Ouyang Kang, 2004)... With a comprehensive view and aiming at comprehensive development, Vietnam promotes and requires universities to promote and exploit in-depth the fields of the industry, while aiming to reduce subjects not in the training field, this not only creates a competitive mechanism between schools but also meets the needs of society.

3. Reform and develop highly applicable higher education

There are many viewpoints and ideas in the world on the issue of reforming higher education. Among them, there are two prominent viewpoints mentioned, especially in the era of integration, deep and wide development, advanced education systems in the world begin to have an interaction that fundamentally changes the philosophy and traditional educational structure of countries. Specifically:

Firstly, university education is considered one of the tools for national orientation and development. Education must be based on state regulations and plans, closely following practical social needs, focusing on solving human resource problems, and providing quality human resources according to the needs of the labour market.

Second, university education must be developed in the direction of becoming a true cultural, teaching and scientific center of society. In other words, university education aims to develop education and open up common knowledge for all humanity, independent of and not dominated by social orientations and developments (Paul Doyon, 2001).

In the author's view, in the process of economic development, human resources are one of the important factors, the driving force for sustainable development of the socio-economy. Therefore, most higher education institutions when building and innovating training programs are mainly based on the opinions of businesses, employers, and even influenced by the actual needs of society, making training knowledge rigid and framework, this situation was also mentioned by the first Minister of Education of Japan - Mori Arinori similarly about the educational situation in Japan that "Education in Japan does not aim to create people who are proficient in arts and sciences, but to train people that the state needs" (Smith, P, 1997). This helps the training program always meet the flexibility and approach to reality. However, training based only on the actual needs of the market is temporary and contains many risks and challenges due to unpredictable fluctuations of the market, and cannot ensure the sustainability of the quality of labor supplied to the market. Because the time of opening majors - recruiting - training majors and occupations compared to the time of actual job recruitment is completely different. In other words, the training program for a profession can become outdated during the training time at school. Therefore, the issue of higher education must always be in a state of movement, change and development to supply human resources according to the inevitable requirements of society in the integration process. However, it is necessary to pay attention and focus on sustainable development in each field and the ability to replace jobs in the labor market.

In addition, the author believes that there are two important factors that determine the success of a university training program. These are "applicability" and "development orientation". The changes and strict demands of the labor market pose great challenges in surveying and developing a plan to reform the training program for learners according to criteria that are close to the market. Changing the training program must take place according to the plan and the amount of knowledge agreed upon for each training program and must always take into account the stability of the subjects in a certain course. Any arbitrary deletion, replacement or addition in teaching always risks losing the balance and logic of the entire program. Therefore, it is not feasible to continuously survey and reform training targets and contents to follow market fluctuations. Therefore, an effective university training program must be applicable. The construction and arrangement of content and output standards for each industry must be based on the development orientation of the market for each group of human resources in a certain period, eliminating the problem of backwardness in traditional teaching methods and contents compared to the progress and fluctuations of the labor market.

In addition, in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic crisis, human resources issues globally in general and in Vietnam in particular are fluctuating and disorienting, accordingly, recruitment orientations and needs in various fields have complicated trends. For example, in human resource management, fundamental changes in working conditions, welfare regimes, and wages have been fundamentally changed by the Covid-19 pandemic, almost completely invalidating the manuals on how to organize human resources, practices used in

human and talent management, performance management, planning and human resource planning are no longer suitable. Therefore, the big problem in higher education institutions today is the balance between professional knowledge and practical thinking methods in the process of educational reform, in order to respond to socio-economic fluctuations, causing the obsolescence of training programs to occur rapidly.

Faced with these difficulties, the author believes that university training should focus on general development orientations, creating a foundation in research thinking, with the goal of creating a workforce with creative thinking and ability, adapting to new fluctuations and challenges, and not being eliminated by market changes. This issue needs to be focused on and developed with specific impacts in the design of applied training programs instead of focusing on opening new professions according to trends, which will easily lead to mass unemployment and being easily eliminated by market fluctuations.

In the face of the trend of international integration, Vietnamese education has also undergone fundamental changes to meet the needs of the socio-economy. However, the approach to new educational methods and approaches needs to be based on selection and creative application in the real context. In the face of constant development, the need for socio-economic innovation, and increasingly competitive labor markets, education, especially higher education, must take the lead as a foundation to pave the way, ready for new steps forward. However, education must still closely follow and aim to serve the country because if education is separate and not in line with the development orientation of the country, that education is not practical and has not achieved effectiveness.

4. Issues related to the socialization of university education

According to the educational reform trend of some countries in the world, the merger of universities will reduce the rate of training facilities. For example, Finland, by passing a new law on education, has merged universities, reducing from more than 20 universities to 15 - 16 universities. The purpose of the merger is to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of universities (Timo Aarrevaara, 2009). In other words, increasing the pressure to go to the university door is considered an effective solution to increase the competitiveness of human resources and the value of university degrees in the labor market of that country. Looking back to 1990, the plan to merge and end the independent existence of universities was established and implemented by the Government of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam with the plan to merge universities operating in parallel into a system of national universities and regional universities with member universities or affiliated schools (Hanoi National University, 2011).

However, as society becomes more civilized and progressive, the level and thinking of the majority of people are improved and oriented towards social values, in which the educational aspect is the most important factor because the need for comprehensive development, training, research and contribution is an essential need of each individual. This is completely consistent with the perception of education in Japan, specifically that learning for Japan's economic success is considered the most important factor, shown through the paradox that they have little confidence in the achievements after the national war but rather their education and training system (Hayes, LD, 1997). On the other hand,

Vietnam has had a deep awareness of the role of higher education in politics, economics and society, and the socialization of higher education is a mandatory goal that the Party and State of Vietnam aim for in order to resolve the above situation. Accordingly, at the 8th Conference of the Central Executive Committee of the Party (term XI) on fundamental and comprehensive innovation of education and training, the Communist Party of Vietnam proposed the policy of "Promoting socialization first of all for vocational education and self-study education" , "Encouraging socialization to invest, build and develop high-quality schools" in Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW dated November 4, 2013 of the Central Executive Committee of the Party (term XI) on fundamental and comprehensive innovation of education and training. However, the issue of socialization of higher education always hides risks in the wrong orientation of training goals and must pay the price with the quality of an entire generation of students, specifically:

Firstly, the issue of socialization of investment capital in the education sector and the promotion of the development of private universities has led to the phenomenon of assimilation between schools and enterprises. However, the assimilation between schools and enterprises needs to be separated from the issue of commercialization of education. Because encouraging individuals and non-state organizations to participate in investment in the development of the education sector can easily lead to the inability to control the exploitation of profits by those individuals and organizations. On the contrary, state control must be placed from the perspective of the obligations to ensure the quality of training and education according to the law of the individuals and organizations making the investment, demonstrating equality in the enjoyment of rights and the implementation of obligations of organizations and individuals operating in the field of educational investment, as well as affirming the position and role of the state in ensuring the quality of training in the situation of socialization of education

Therefore, the author believes that the assimilation between schools and businesses is not only understood as ignoring the quality of education but also as focusing on exploiting the number of student inputs, seriously reducing the output standards of the industry, even distorting the standard knowledge of human resources. As presented above, along with the right to enjoy the profits from the investment in the education sector, the obligation to ensure the development and implementation of educational plans, improving the quality of training services according to the prescribed level is a mandatory commitment to the state and subject to sanctions when violated. For example, at the end of 2011, the Ministry of Education and Training announced the results of the inspection and suspension of enrollment in 2012 for more than ten training majors of a number of universities and colleges because they did not meet the mandatory regulations on the ratio of students/permanent lecturers and did not ensure facilities (Linh Giang, 2012).

Second, the fragmentation and decline in training efficiency of private universities stem from the current situation of a sharp increase in the number of universities over the years. Accordingly, as of 2020, there were 236 universities nationwide, of which 61 were private universities, accounting for about 26% of the total number of universities in the country (MSc. Nguyen Thai Hoang, 2021). This situation has weakened the state's ability to control the organization of activities, as well as the training quality of teaching programs

through inspection and examination, creating opportunities for negative aspects in training, leading to increasingly fierce differentiation between university groups.

In that situation, the improvement and complete elimination of the phenomenon of uniformity between enterprises and schools, not focusing on training human resources quality is one of the urgent issues in the current period for the reform of higher education. At the same time, it is necessary to drastically implement plans to ensure the implementation of obligations in the development and reform of educational quality of organizations and individuals participating in investment. Accordingly, in order to achieve the expected results in ensuring educational quality at training institutions, it is necessary to first aim to improve the educational quality management mechanisms from state agencies to training institutions. In particular, the issue of educational accreditation at certain stages is considered an effective work to help the state control over the quality of higher education always be guaranteed and promptly detect violations for handling according to regulations.

Realizing the importance of educational quality assessment in training institutions. The Ministry of Education and Training has issued Circular No. 38/2013/TT-BGDĐT regulating the process and cycle of quality assessment of training programs of universities, colleges and vocational secondary schools, laying the foundation for strict control of the corresponding training tasks at schools in the current period. Accordingly, Article 4 of Circular No. 38/2013/TT-BGDĐT stipulates the process of quality assessment of training programs taking place in 4 stages including : i) Self-assessment; ii) External assessment, re-assessment (if any); iii) Assessment of assessment results; iv) Recognition of meeting educational quality standards . Accordingly, when going through the self-assessment stage approved by the Internal Self-Assessment Council on the basis of collected and processed evidence, the Self-Assessment Council will write a self-assessment report. This is an important basis for moving to the external assessment and re-assessment stage. However, at this stage, the author finds some shortcomings in legal regulations that may affect the assessment of training quality.

As analyzed above, organizations and individuals participating in investment in the training sector necessarily have the right to enjoy profits from that investment activity, but must always be responsible for training and training quality assessment is a form for the state to check the implementation of the commitments of the above-mentioned investing organizations and individuals according to Clause 3, Article 3 of Circular No. 38/2013/TT-BGDĐT. However, in Article 14 of Circular No. 38/2013/TT-BGDĐT, educational institutions register for external assessment of training programs with an educational quality assessment organization licensed to operate by the Ministry of Education and Training, so it can be said that the training quality assessment organization does not belong to the state but is licensed to operate by a competent authority. Based on the request of the educational institution, the educational quality assessment organization signs a contract with the educational institution to assess the self-assessment report of the training program according to Clause 1, Article 15 of Circular 38/2013/TT-BGDĐT. It can be said that external assessment and re-assessment arise on the basis of a contract, the nature of which is to demonstrate equality in the agreement to establish, change and terminate the rights and obligations of the parties according to Article 385 of the 2015 Civil Code. The author believes that the issue of educational quality assessment cannot be based on an

equal agreement but must ensure independence between the assessment subject and the subject being assessed. Establishing a contract between the quality assessment organization and the organization being assessed may negatively affect the assessment results, leading to failure to fulfill the task of explaining to competent state management agencies and society about the quality status of the training program as prescribed.

Furthermore, unlike organizations and individuals participating in investment in the education sector who can exploit profits during the investment process, the evaluation of training programs, or specifically for entities licensed by the Ministry of Education and Training, must not contain commercial aspects in the operating mechanism. Because this is considered an important activity to help the state control the implementation of education and training activities at higher education institutions, ensure the ability to fulfill obligations and commitments to investment in the education sector, promptly eliminate degenerate educational institutions that do not meet the criteria for training programs, avoid huge consequences in the training process and supply of qualified human resources to the labor market.

In addition, similar to the commercial nature, the possibility of competition in training quality inspection activities among entities licensed by the Ministry of Education and Training to conduct accreditation activities needs to be completely eliminated. Accordingly, quality accreditation organizations are not established by competent state agencies but only licensed to conduct quality accreditation activities, so there are currently no documents regulating the quantity and operating mechanism of each organization. On the other hand, the basis for conducting educational quality assessment for external assessment and re-assessment is based on the contract between the educational quality assessment organization and the educational institutions. Therefore, the external assessment and re-assessment activities of quality accreditation organizations still have a civil-social nature, which risks leading to competition in the issue of assessment organization, causing negative effects in the assessment results. These negative aspects will affect the reliability of using external assessment and re-assessment results - this is the basis for educational institutions with assessed training programs to implement improvement plans, enhance educational quality and for the Education Quality Assessment Council of the education quality assessment organization to appraise, propose consideration, recognition or non-recognition of training programs that meet educational quality standards as prescribed in Article 19 of Circular 38/2013/TT-BGDĐT.

From the above analysis, the author finds that there is a need for intervention by competent authorities in directing and defining the scope and field of operation of each quality assessment organization. The establishment and recognition of the activities of quality assessment organizations must be based on the plan of competent authorities. At the same time, lawmakers need to consider eliminating the contractual mechanism in requiring the implementation of quality assessment of training programs between educational quality assessment organizations and educational institutions, instead adding legal provisions binding the responsibility of state agencies in receiving assessment requests from training institutions and designating educational quality assessment organizations to conduct assessment upon request.

5. Conclusion

Higher education is one of the important factors to promote sustainable economic and social development. This is an important challenge for education and training in higher education institutions, a practical experiment, reflecting the quality of education and training in a specific field. Therefore, higher education does not stand still in isolation from the continuous development of the economy, but must always change and adapt in the training program to meet practical needs. However, the change and reform of higher education must aim at the goal of training human resources with high adaptability to market fluctuations through the ability to think, create, apply and research, avoiding being eliminated according to the rules of the market due to the constraints and "numbness" of school knowledge, taking the sustainable development of education as the core content of reform. In general, integrating sustainable development into education brings positive effects to training institutions, but the burden of budget and funding is one of the major challenges (Nhan Cam Tri, 2022) that the Party and State of Vietnam must inevitably aim to socialize higher education to attract investment from individuals and non-state organizations in the education sector. However, the socialization of education must always focus on building strict regulations on responsibilities in ensuring the quality of education. At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen and promote the role of the state in inspecting and handling violations of ensuring the quality of education of higher education institutions through perfecting regulations on quality assessment of higher education.

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